

DETERMINING THE NEEDS OF MOTHERS WITH AT LEAST THREE INTELLECTUAL DISABLED CHILDREN

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Abstract:

The purpose of this research is to determine the needs of mothers with three intellectually disabled children. This study has been held with the participation of eleven volunteer mothers, living in Diyarbakır province in 2017. Semi-structured interview technique was used as qualitative research methods in the research. Based on the findings obtained from the research, it was determined that the mothers had important requirements such as materiality, information, general and social support, and needs of expressing themselves to the environment about the disability of their children. The biggest topic was determined as the lack of time for their personal development. When the national and international literatures are analyzed, it has been determined that in Turkey needs of the mothers with three intellectual disabled children are higher than those of the developed countries. The main needs are knowledge and materiality. Based on this points, especially mainly legal positive discrimination, governmental agencies, educational institutions and NGO's need to be more sensitive and should make concrete steps by meeting the needs of children with multiple disabilities.

Keywords: intellectual disabilities, needs of mother, maternal requirement, special requirement

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1. Introduction

Neither mothers nor fathers does not expect bringing a child to the world with disability, in other words, parents are not prepared to be a mother or a father of a child with intellectual disability. Despite, all parents want to have smart, talented and also successful children. (Metin, 2012)

Parents who have still wait long time and have dreams and expectations about their baby, are disappointed by learning that it will be a child with special needs. Because of this situation, families with children born with special needs experience very complex feelings; they do not know what to do, how to receive help, where to go, and most importantly, how the live will be with an intellectually disabled baby. (Çiftçi Tekinarslan, 2010; Metin, 2012)

Even though their feelings like shock, denial, rejection, suffering, guilt, indecision, anger, embarrassment and unacceptability, parents try to get adapt to live with this situation which just happens completely opposite according to their expectations. They are looking for solutions to the situation (Darıca, 2000).

Intellectual disability is usually a persistent and unchangeable status. Hence, meeting the needs of the mentally disabled children brings continuous and difficult phases for the families. In addition to the needs such as care, education and health of the disabled child, social attitudes and judgements, uncertainties about the future evolution of the children with disabilities, are sources of stress factors for the family. When the stress factors cannot be handled in a right way, these stress accumulations may cause emotional problems for the whole family. (Dereli and Okur, 2008; Turan, 2009; Çapa, 2009; Karadağ, 2009)

Many of the mentally disabled children can be clearly distinguished from their healthy peers because of their physical appearance. By taking also into consideration the viewpoint of the society to an intellectual disabled child, the family faces more uncomfortable situations, which can also negatively affect the whole family. (Karadağ, 2009)

In environments where people are crowded like shopping malls, markets, areas where events are held, etc., the possibility is higher to have a problem with peoples, families are forced to escape from the people in their surroundings and push themselves to loneliness (Çapa, 2009). Because of this reasons, families neither want to talk about their children nor about their children's disabilities (Turan, 2009).

Thus, many organizations and field specialists who individually serve for people who have special needs have focused only on peoples with mental disability for a long time, but were not focused on the families. Nowadays, it is more clear that identifying and meeting the needs of the families with intellectual disability children, means

eliminating the needs of the intellectual disabled children (Kaner, 2009). Because the family is experiencing an unexpected situation with the diagnosis of the child, they are entering a new phase in which the needs of the child needs to be met and the various needs for them are revealed (Russel, 2003; Cavkaytar, 2010; Küllü, 2008). The needs of most families differ from each other depending on the child's needs. These requirements may vary depending on the type and severity of the disability, the age, the sex of the child, multiple disabilities in the family, and multiple obstacles in the child. Depending on these points, every family has different requirements (Reichman, Corman and Noonan, 2008; Sucuoğlu, 2000; Evcimen, 1996).

Because families will need many needs that was not are requirement before the diagnosis and the recognition of the child (Cavkaytar, 2010), many studies conducted in the field of special education, is emphasized that the services to be provided should be planned not only to meet the needs of special needs individuals, but should cover all the members in the family. (Şardağ, 2010)

By comparing Turkey and international literature, many studies have been done to determine the needs of families with intellectual disability children.

When we look at studies conducted in our country: Öztürk-Tokuç (2009) found that mothers who have children with autism have expressed their need for information about their children's behavior and communication problems as a result of their work on their experiences.

Sola (2008) conducted a study to determine the needs of mothers with premature and low birth weight babies under risk of developmental retardation. At the end of the study, it was seen that the mothers expressed mainly their information needs. It is understood that mothers need more time to talk with the doctor or nurse who is interested in the situation of their child.

Evcimen (1996) found that the support and material requirements of mothers and fathers were different when they tried to determine the needs of parents with children with mental retardation. In addition, also the increase on children's ages and the number of disabled children changes the requirements of the families.

Akçamete ve Kargın (1996) conducted a study to determine the needs of mothers with hearing-impaired children. As a result of the research, the main requirement was determined as knowledge. Mothers want to be aware on how to teach their children to give some skills. As a second matter, mothers' requirements were materiality requirements.

By the study from Çetinkaya ve Öz (2000), which was measuring the effect of giving planned information to the parents about their children, it was found out that, mothers of children with cerebral palsy, seeking for information about their children disease, treatment and rehabilitation.

By a study of Ender, Kocabaş, Arslan and Özaydın (2011), the study of the stress levels and needs of families with children with disabilities; have reached the conclusion that parents need information about the situation of children with disabilities.

Mert (1997) found that parents who have children in different disability groups have common needs and which is mainly knowledge. In terms of knowledge, it has been seen that parents primarily need the information about institutions that their children can benefit from for now and in the future times.

Öztürk (2011) conducted a survey on the purpose of determining the needs and the burden of the families with disabled children. When summarizing the survey, mothers indicated that their main need is knowledge and at very least need of the families, is to explain their child's disability to other peoples.

When reviewing international field literature; Sontag and Schacht (1994) compared the participation and knowledge requirements of early intervention programs of parents in different cultures in their research. As a result, it was seen that parent's main requirement was knowledge. Fitzpatrick, Angus, Smith, and Doug Coyle (2008), in their study, conducted a study to determine the needs of families and the services that are important to the families after learning their children's hearing impairment. In this study, it was seen that parents need information about their children, social services, and so on. Reyes-Blanes Correa and Bailey (1999) conducted a study to compare the needs of parents who have perceived their child's disability, with parents living in Puerto Rico and Florida. The results of the research show that the children of the mothers living in Porto-Rico needs information about their rights and need more social support.

Buran, Sawin, Grayson and Criss (2009) conducted a study to determine the needs of families with children with cerebral palsy. As a result of the research, it has emerged that most families need services for the children. The other area that parents needed was information and care. Wang and Michaels (2009); In the People's Republic of China, they worked on the needs of families with severely disabled children, result of this study families with children with severe disabilities have shown that they need more social services. According to this study, need for social services are followed by information needs, family and social support needs.

When we look at the results of these studies, the needs of families often differ from each other. These studies have mainly dealt with families with a child with disabilities. In these studies, the need for information is intensively noteworthy, and it expresses mother's needs predominantly. In the studies conducted, the negative impact which of the disabled child created in the family, mostly affecting the mother. (Kazak and Marvin, 1984) Mothers always take the responsibility of their intellectual disability children and normal children. Because of this responsibility of mothers, they have given

up most of the roles they have the rates of participation in cultural and social life have also decreased very seriously. (Okanlı and Ekinci 2004) This is caused by the fact that mother's spent a large part of their time at home with intellectual disability children. (Kazak, 1986)

The care needs of intellectual disability child are usually made by the mothers and the mothers take more responsibility. (Öztürk, 2011) This responsibility sometimes affects the mother in the negative and can cause more stress. This increased stress is often reflected in the husband and other children. Harmony problems and some behavior problems can also arise in healthy siblings of children with disabilities and caused some familial problems. (Küçüker, 1993; Küllü, 2008) That is why the needs of the mothers should be addressed and solved first. It is known that the identification and resolution of maternal needs will reduce stress and discomfort on the family. This will make the family feel that they are not alone and it provides that more efforts for their children with disabilities. As the needs and expectations of the families are determined and met, for the disabled children and their families' conditions life which is much more difficult than for healthy people in the society, it will be made easier.

The main purpose of evaluating family needs is to determine the nature, content and quality of the service to be provided to the child and the family, but also to better support the development of children with mental retardation. (Bailey and Simeonsson, 1988; Cavkaytar, Ceyhan, Adıgüzel, Uysal and Garan, 2012; Durualp, Kocabaş, Arslan and Özaydın, 2011)

The purpose of this research is to determine the material needs, information needs, disclosure requirements and general support-social service needs of mothers of children with at least three intellectual disability.

2. Method

This section includes the research model, the characteristics of participants, the collection of data and the analysis of data.

2.1. Research Model

This research is a qualitative research aimed at determining the needs of mothers with at least three children with mental retardation. The data collection process utilized a semi-structured interview technique used in qualitative research.

2.2. Working group

Working group, selected by purposeful sampling method. This group was formed by volunteers living in the provincial center of Diyarbakır and mothers with at least 3 children with intellectual disability.

Table 1: Properties of mothers

Demographic Properties of the Mothers											
Mother's name	Education status	Age	Job	Monthly income of family	the total number of children	Number of disabled children	Gender of disabled children	Age of disabled children	Levels of disabled children's	Did receive any education about the children situation?	How does you feel?
Songül	primary school	37	Housewife	2500 TL	5	3	Boy (3)	8,11,15	Light(1) Middle(1) Heavy(1)	No	Comfortable
Şükran	primary school	37	Housewife	2000 TL	6	4	Boy (4)	4,11,16,18	Light(2) Middle(2)	No	Anxious
Saime	primary school	38	Housewife	2000 TL	4	3	Boy (3)	9,11,18	Heavy (1) Middle(2)	No	Anxious
Zeynep	illiterate	46	Housewife	2500 TL	8	4	Boy(3) Girl(1)	16,19 20,26	Very Heavy (4)	No	Restless
Hicran	illiterate	38	Housewife	2500 TL	4	3	Boy(2) Girl(1)	7,11,14	Very Heavy (1) Heavy (2)	No	Restless
Sude	primary school	38	Housewife	3000 TL	5	3	Boy(2) Girl(1)	5,10,13	Middle (2) Light (1)	No	Anxious
Esmâ	illiterate	55	Housewife	3000 TL	3	3	Boy(3)	23,25 28	Very Heavy (3)	No	Restless
Meliha	primary school	32	Housewife	2000 TL	3	3	Boy(1) Girl (2)	2,5,10	Lght (2) Middl (1)	No	Restless
Senem	primary school	33	Housewife	8500 TL	5	3	Boy (2) Girl(1)	5,11,13	Light (3)	No	Anxious
Melahat	primary school	38	Housewife	2000 TL	5	3	Boy(3)	11,13,15	Heavy (3)	No	Anxious
Nevin	primary school	45	Housewife	2000 TL	4	3	Boy(2) Girl(1)	10,10,6	Heavy (3)	No	Anxious

The ages of the mothers participating in the study group ranged between 32-46, 3 mothers stated that they couldn't read and write, while 8 mothers reported that they were primary school graduates.

All of the mothers in the scope of the interview were housewives and they stated that their monthly family income was in the range of 2000-3000 TL; only one mother stated that her monthly family income was 8500 TL. The total number of children in the homes varies between 3 and 8. 3 children of 9 mothers and 4 children of 2 mothers are intellectual disability. While the average age of disabled children is 2-28, 9 children are mild, 8 children are middle, 10 children are heavy and 8 children are very heavy intellectual disability. Mothers stated that they didn't go to any course related to their

children disability. One of the mothers said that she felt comfortable, 4 mothers were restless, 6 mothers were worried.

2.3. Development of Data Collection Tool and Collection of Data

Semi-structured interview method was used to collect data in the study. Using the related literature, appropriate interview questions were decided for the purpose of the research and personal information form was added and opinions were obtained from two lecturers in the field. After the expert opinions, interview questions and personal information form were given the final form. The interview form used in the research consists of two parts. The first part includes 12 questions about the personal information of the mothers. And the second part contains 11 open-ended questions to determine the needs of the mothers.

2.4. Validity and Reliability

In order to ensure the validity of the survey, interview questions were obtained by taking into consideration the opinions of a field expert. The interview form was created by inspecting the appropriate area for the purpose and taking the opinion of two experts. The content that has been made is appropriate for the purpose of researching the themes in the analysis. For the internal reliability of the study, the analysis of the data obtained from the participants, the conversion of the responses into codes, the creation and interpretation of themes were performed independently by two researchers and a consistency study was conducted.

2.5. Analysis of Data

In the analysis of data collected from interviews, content analysis technique was used. After the negotiations were completed, the researcher gathered the voice records from the interview and composed the article. Every voice heard during the recording of the voice recordings was written as it was heard, without any corrections, additions or subtractions in the order of interviewer-interviewed parties.

In order to share information of the interviews, without sharing the personal information of the interviewed mothers and without causing any confusion, the first interviewed mother was named as A1 and subsequent codes were given to each mother by order of the interview. Based on interview questions and field knowledge, sub-themes were formed based on themes and answers given by the participants.

3. Findings

This section includes a comparison of the information given by the mothers who participated in the interview and the literature.

The findings of the study consist of 4 themes and sub-themes of these 4 themes. The four themes that make up the findings of the research are listed as follows:

Mothers With at Least 3 intellectual disability Children,

3.1. Opinions for materiality requirements

3.2. Opinions of mothers, about the information they give to the society about the their children situation

a. The announcement of the situation from their disabled children, to their healthy children.

b. What to say to neighbors, friends or foreigners when they ask about the situation of their disabled children.

3.3. Mothers opinions about knowledge requirements

a. Opinions on how to teach some skills to their children

b. Opinions of mothers about their children condition (disability)

c. Opinions about information exchange with other disabled children's parents

3.4 General support requirements

a. Opinions about the need to talk more with a clergyman who think they can help solve their problems.

b. Opinions about a caretaker who will be take care of their children when necessary

c. Opinions about who they usually prefer to talk about their problems

d. When they are attending a meeting (such as neighbors and relatives), their opinions on where they will leave their children.

d1. When going to a meeting (such as neighbors and relatives meetings), the views of the nursing home or nursery where they can receive appropriate care for their child.

3.1. Mothers Opinions about Material Needs

The interviewed mothers reported different opinions about their material needs. Frequency distribution of the information given by the mothers regarding this topic is given in the following table.

Table 2: Thoughts about Material Needs

Matter	f
Unable to cover costs	10
Unable to pay their rent	7
Unable to buy tools and toys	7
Unable to buy clothes	6
Can not afford educational expenses	3

On the interview we made with the mothers in the study group, 10 of the mothers expressed their material need as *'The cost of my intellectual disability children is very heavy, I can not afford it'*.

Mrs Songül *'We need financial help, we are unable to pay our rent, we can not really afford the cost of these three children, sometimes the people around us are helping us.'* She has drawn attention to the costs of three disabled children. About this subject, Mrs Sude *'we are trying to meet all our needs from the daily money that my husband brings home and the care paid for children. We're trying to cover the costs of children as much as we can. We still can not raise the expense, it is too heavy'*. She said that they as parents could not meet their needs.

Most of the 10 mothers about their material needs stated that they could not fulfill the requests because of financial difficulties. Mrs Meliha *'We are living with care paid for my children. My husband is unemployed, we have no home. Most of the time I can not cover things that my children wants.'* Then Mrs Nevin, who came from Syria and settled in this country, *'the villagers gave us a house and was welcomed by food and drink aid lovers. We have no means of transportation; I do not get anything my children want.'* They expressed their material needs with that expression.

Seven mothers informed that they could not pay their rent because of their economic situation. Mrs Şükran *'We have so many expenses that I do not know which one to grow up with. My husband is not working; he can not leave us to work. We move to the family of my husband, because we cannot pay our rent, we live with them; we try to manage with the care paid for children. But it's not enough'*. On the same topic Mrs Saime *'I can't pay my home rent, sometimes my brother pays my rent. I live in Toki 80 m2 house, 500 TL rent, my husband is unemployed. The money I get is not enough for my children.'* They also stated that they were unable to pay even their house rents.

Seven of the mothers we interviewed about financial requirements say *'I can not get the necessary tools and toys for my children'*. In this context, the mother we interviewed Mrs. Şükran *'we have no other income than the paid which gave for my children care. I could not even get a toy for my children, our neighborhood is bringing toys and clothes while in town but I have not received anything for my children since we came to the village, sometimes they give it from the school, sometimes they give it from the rehabilitation center'*.

Mrs Hicran *'our budget is too limited, I can not always fulfill the demands of my children, I can not get any toys they want'*. They are stressed by their financial needs.

Six of the mothers in the study group stated that *'their children can only get their saturate'* Mrs Songül *'we do not have a budget for the future of the children, so we can not prepare a piece of it, the money comes only to them and their throats. The state is paying the maintenance fee (the youngest child) for Kadir, but we can not get the other two. There are sensitive people in the environment, they are helping us. Our family physician gives us both financial and spiritual help.'* she pointed that the money passed to the hands is inadequate.

Within the same scope Mrs Hicran *'This is not enough money for them (children mean). Rent, gas, electricity, water bill, not really enough, how do I become my carer? You tell. The money I get is not enough for my children's throat '* she stated that the material requirements were in the strictest sense.

Six of the mothers said *'they often couldn't bought clothes for their children'* Mrs Melahat *'My economic situation is very bad I can not get anything for my children, everything is expensive, but I can fill my children bellies, it was a feast(eid) but I didn't get clothes for my children.'*

On the same topic, Mrs Meliha *'My children need so much but as basic necessities I get my children's clothes most times from my neighbors, sometimes they send clothes from my children's school.'*

Three of the interviewed mothers were informing about their financial needs *'They stated that their children's education costs were too heavy and they could not afford this needs'* about this subject Mrs Saima *'We can't want anything from anybody, we have to pay a lot of money for the children's education, I have a daughter other than these children, and she goes to high school, these 3 disabled kids go to school. Most of the time I am not able to give money to my children. I'm paying all the expenses again for the maintenance. Children's clothes bring neighbors, Veysel's teacher brings clothes for my children. Not only children with disabilities that other children have educational expenses and that she has to manage only the amount of care paid for his children. Mrs Şükran *'we have so much expense that I can not send some of my children to the school because of this expense. So I can not afford these costs. Nobody's helping us'* saying that she did not send some children to the school because of economic reasons.*

3.2. Opinions of mothers about their children situation, information which they give to the neighborhood

a. The announcement of the situation from their disabled children, to their healthy children.

The frequency distribution of the question *'What kind of explanation did you give to your healthy children about the situation of your special needs children?'* Is given in the table below.

Table 3: Opinions about how your children explain their situation to their brothers and sisters

Matter	F
Do not make any comments	4
Healthy children know the situation of their brothers/sisters better.	4
Do not need to explain because they grow together	3
Healthy child is too young for understand	2

The mothers interviewed stated that what kind of information they gave to the environment related to the situation of children with intellectual disability. The first item on this subject *'How did you explain the situation of your children to the siblings?'* for this question, 4 of the 11 mothers stated that they did not make any explanation because their children with disabilities did not have enough information about their situation. 4 mothers in the same scope stated that healthy children have more information about the situation of their disabled siblings. In this regard Mrs Songül *'I needed to tell, but I did not know anything. But now they are aware of everything, they know the situation of their brothers well from me, but it would be better if they were conscious beforehand. When my children were born nobody told me anything, my first child born doctors: 'It will be blind or they will not walk'.* Mrs Saime, in the same context gave an opinion *'I couldn't explain to my children, I didn't know exactly what I'm going to tell, but my daughter knows better because she search everything on the internet'* they stated that their children were not well informed about the situation but that healthy children had more information about the situation of their disabled brothers.

Three of the mothers who participated in the study, indicated that their healthy children and children with disabilities were grown together, so they did not feel the need to make any explanation. About this subject Mrs Zeynep *'I didn't make any statement, they have already grown up with my normal children, sometimes they are bored, they are angry, they say, 'Mom, these are the big problems for us and we are not comfortable with them.'* Sometimes they take them to their laps, they love them. I mean, our home is like intensive care, Mrs Hicran *'I did not make any explanation, they grown up with together'*. She said.

In this study, two mothers stated that their normal children did not make any statement because they were too young. A mother gave information about the feelings and behaviors of children with disabilities. About this subject Mrs Melahat *'I tell them that their psychology is a little different, they get angry quickly, how to approach them.'* She said.

b. What to say to neighbors, friends or foreigners when they ask about the situation of their disabled children.

The frequency distribution of the answers to the question 'What are you answer when your neighbor, friend or a foreigner's ask about your children disability?' Is the following on the table.

Table 4: Answers given by mothers to neighbors, friends, or children of a foreigner

Matter	f
She says what he heard from teachers and doctors	8
She says that it comes from God, that it is the blessing of God	5

We asked mothers 'What do you answer to them when your neighbor, your friend, or foreign ask about your children situation?' 8 mothers said we got information from teacher and the doctor about the subject and mothers gave this information to no matter who ask.

Mrs Sude 'when somebody asks about my children obstacle, I couldn't answer before. Just I said it's my destiny. Then I learned a lot from doctors, teachers, now when someone asks a question about my children, I tell them what doctors and teachers say 'used expression.

Mrs Nevin 'I said it is the appreciation of God, I fired when I was pregnant, so my children were like that. But other children was burn in Turkey, doctors said we had a blood incompatibility, the needle did this child was normal, I think now would be like blood in the dispute. And when they ask, I say that what i heard from doctor'. She stated that she didn't know their children situation before and now she know obstacle come from blood disagreement with his husband.

In this study, 5 mothers explained the situation of their children to the surrounding area and stated that this situation came from God or that it was a blessing from God. In this regard, Mrs Zeynep said, 'I say" it is appreciation of God, I do not have a consanguineous marriage. I say it is my fortune.' Mrs Hicran 'I am saying that they are an appreciation of God. Nobody's asking. We can not get out of the house.' They answered the questions asked with their testimony.

3.3. Opinions on Information Requirements

a. Opinions on how to teach some skills to their children

The frequency distribution of the responses to the question "how do you teach some skills of your special needs children" that we ask you to answer is in the table below.

Table 5: Opinions on how to teach some skills to their children

Matter	f
I can not find time to teach	5
I do not know how to teach	4
Repeat what you do	4
Applying what teachers say	3

Within the scope of the research, we were asking 'How do you teach some skills to your children', 5 mothers said that did not have time to teach their children a skill. About this issue Mrs Meliha '*Children learn on their own. They are in the streets until the evening, teaching at school. I do not have the opportunity; I do not have the time I took all the burden of the house. I can not teach.* About this issue Mrs Saima '*just I can do the child care*' ı *can't teach some skills because I do not have time. I can barely meet children's care needs*'.

Four of the mothers we interviewed, said that tried to teach some skills, but they don't know exactly how to teach them. Mrs Şükran '*I show them as much as I can. My two middle-aged boys understand better and do it. The big one does not want to do it. But I do not know exactly how to teach, I can not teach like teachers*'.

One of the four mothers who try to teach their children by repeating some skills, Mrs Songül '*every game and each skill is different, I do not know how to teach; but I repeat what I do to them*'.

The 3 mothers we interviewed stated that what teachers said had applied their sayings. Mrs Senem about this subject '*usually my children learn at school, sometimes I show little things that teachers say, like wearing shoes. I'm telling something about skills. I'm showing them*'.

b. Opinions about obstacles of their children

The frequency distribution of the answers to the questions 'what can you say about the information about your disabled children' that we ask the mothers is in the table below.

Table 6: Opinions of information about their children disability

Matter	f
ı havent enough information about obstacle of my children	7
Having the information that doctors say	5
Having information which teachers said	4

In the question 'what can you say about your children obstacle', we asked. 7 of mothers said that there is not enough information about obstacle of children. In this regard, Mrs Esma '*I do not know what happened, three of my children are the same (heavy disabled) they don't understand what they are listening. They were very good at first when they were children,*

suddenly they become disabled, we came from village here for treatment, doctors found no remedy,' she said that has not enough knowledge about the disabled of their children.

Mrs Sude *'When my child started the first school, teacher called me and said that the child had some problems. and he said that he want to lead me to the research center for my child, I already had some doubts about the situation of my child, I learned my child's situation there first, they told me there that my child was mildly intellectual disability, afterward we went to the hospital and got some tests, doctors said same. But I have not enough informed about my children's disability.'*

In the same context, 5 mothers said that they just have information which they got from doctor about disabilities. Mrs Senem *'I learned the situation of my children from the doctors. My children have been anaerobic during childbirth, but their condition is not so heavy, it doesn't really distinguished from normal child.'* Within the same scope, Mrs Nevin used this testimony *'At first we were not informed, the children were crying for the first three months and we took them to the doctor. Doctor said these children (twins) are disabled. After that, my husband and I were very sad and we supported each other. My husband's first wife, (Kuma) has not her child, she helped us a lot.'*

Mrs Meliha who is one of the 4 mothers whose get information about their children handicap from teachers *'I learned from the teacher of my first child's situation, told me that the level of the child was a little behind, then the teachers in the guidance research center said the same thing and gave some information about my child's disability.'* she stated that the child was informed about the obstacle situation from the teachers.

a. Opinions about information exchange with parents with other intellectual disability children

We asked mothers *'What can you say about exchanging information with parents who have other intellectual disability children'* The frequency distribution of the answers to the question is given in the following table.

Table 7: Opinions about information exchange with parents with other special needs children

Matter	f
It would be useful	7
Not enough time	5
New things can be learned, can be supported	4
It will not be useful	2

Seven of the mothers who were interviewed stated that would be very useful for the question *'What can you say about information exchange with mothers and fathers with children with other special needs'*.

Mrs Melahat *'I think it will be very useful because the parents want to do something constantly for their children. Maybe they have a good doctor; maybe they've found a good medicine. This will be good share'*. 5 mothers about this subject said that there was no time for this, but it would be useful. In this context, Mrs Saime *'I say it is very useful. We can learn something from them but I have not spare time for my self. How we get together. I do children's care until the night, I do housework. I can not go to bazaar'*. Mrs Saime said that *'it would be very useful in this matter, but because of the time it would be difficult to achieve this.'* 4 mothers said that *'We can learn new things from other mothers and fathers, we can support each other'*. For this matter Mrs Songül *'Believe it, to be able to talk to family and exchange information can be very useful. Maybe they tried something new. Maybe what I do is good for them. Different ideas emerge, we support each other because we have the best of us understand each other.'* she said. Mrs Esma, one of the two mothers who said that they would not benefit from sharing information *'the situation of my children is very heavy. They can't speak, can't play, they just lay. Now what will I learn from other parents, doctors said for my children can not live any longer. This is my destiny'*.

All of the children of two mothers who have negative opinions about exchanging information with parents who have other special needs children are dependent on the bed because they are mentally disabled at a very severe level. These negative expressions by the mothers may be due to the severe handicap of the children.

3.4 General Support and Community Service Requirements

Mothers who were interviewed had their opinions on 4 items about general support and social service needs. These views are listed as follows.

- a) Opinions about the need to talk more with clergyman whom they think they can help solve their problems;
 - b) What is their opinion about a caretaker who will take care of their children when necessary;
 - c) Opinions about who they usually prefer to talk about their problems;
 - d) When they are attending a meeting (such as neighbors and relatives), their opinions on where they will leave their children.
- a. Opinions about the need to talk more with clergy whom they think they can help solve their problems.

We asked mother *'Do you think the clergy can help you to solve your problems?'* The frequency distribution of the answers to the question is in the following table.

Table 8: Opinions about more conversation with clergy to solve their problem

Matter	f
I can not see any benefit	6
Spiritual relaxation	4
Do not feel the need to go	3

We asked mothers ‘Do you think that the clergyman can help you solve your problems?’ for this question 6 mothers went to the clergy for the first disabled children but stated that they did not see any benefit and that there was no difference in the case of their children. For this subject Mrs Saima ‘There is no benefit, before I went there with Veysel but I didn’t see any benefit. But I never took these two little kids. Mrs Şükran ‘Once we went with my husband. He read, blew, wrote something. But there was no difference. After that, we went to the doctor. The doctors told us not to go to places like this, look at schools for their training’ she said.

The mothers who said that ‘I was relieved spiritually’, Mrs Senem ‘it did not really benefit us, but at least I was spiritually relaxed, telling us about the innocence of children, the sanctity of what we will do’ expressed spiritual comfort with her expression.

Under the title of the same topic ‘I never heard the need to go’ Mrs Melahat ‘No I did not go this is a hospital situation, doctors can not find a solution. The clergy never find me a cure.’ she said.

b. opinion about a carer who will take care of their children when necessary

The frequency distribution of the answers to the question 'what do you think about a carrier who can care for your children when you need' is included in the following table.

Table 9: Opinions about a carer who children will be taken care of when necessary

Matter	f
The load on the top is reduced	8
Can devote time to itself	6
Economic challenges	6
Distrust	3

We asked mothers, what are your opinions about a carer who will be taking care of your child in cases where it is necessary? 8 mothers would be very good and their burden would be reduced. 6 mother stated that their economic situation made it impossible and 3 mother stated that they could not trust the caregiver.

About this topic Mrs Sude ‘my economic situation is not good at all, if my children were someone to look after, at least I could do other things in my house, maybe I would go to a neighbor for half an hour, she expressed the situation like this.

Mrs Zeynep 'I can not go to a wedding, I can not sit with a relative, I have to go to a doctor but I can not go I mean I can not take a minute myself, I always struggle with my children, she said,

Mrs Songül ' It would be great if we had a carer but we do not have a carer, we already have no money to give it to carer, I and my daughters are looking my children'. She reveals the material direction of the problem.

Mrs Esmâ 'I do not trust the caregiver, I can't leave my children to caregiver. my children, can't talk, nor do anything. As long as I live I will look after my children, she used this expression'

c. opinions about who they usually prefer to talk about their problems

The following table shows the frequency distribution of the responses to the question "Who do you prefer talking about your problems?"

Table 10: Opinions about who they usually prefer to talk about their problems

Matter	f
Speak to a psychologist or psychiatrist	6
Speaking with non-family members	4
Talk to the mother	2

In the scope of the research, we asked mothers who would you prefer to talk about your problems?' 6 mothers stated that they wanted to talk to psychologists or psychiatrists.

Mrs Şükran, 'we have financial needs, my husband does not work, the situation of my children is bad. We live with my husband's family. Sometimes I cry, I keep thinking about it, I can not find someone to tell my story, I feel overwhelmed I sometimes need a psychologist for speaking.'

Mrs Songül about this topic 'I want to talk to someone who is out of my family. But it don't condemn me, and don't recognize me, it's enough' she said.

Mrs Melahat 'my mother always supports me, sometimes helping me in the care of my children. Sometimes it meets the needs of the house. Just my mother can understand me. '

d. When they are attending a meeting (such as neighbors and relatives), their opinions on where they will leave their children

The following questionnaire shows the frequency distribution of the question "Where do you leave your children when you go to a meeting (such as meetings in your neighbors and relatives)?"

Table 11: When they are attending a meeting (such as neighbors and relatives), their opinions on where they will leave their children

Matter	f
I never leave my children to anywhere	7
Leave relatives	4

Six of the mothers interviewed indicated that they could not leave their children at any time when they attended a meeting (such as neighbors and relatives). About this topic Mrs Esma '*All three of my children are in need of my care, I can't take them to anywhere and I don't leave them to anybody for care*'. From within the mothers who saying I leave my children to relatives for their care, Mrs Meliha said '*I can't leave my children, but when I need so much I call my mother, she comes and look after my children*'. Nevin Hanım, the mother who came to Syria and settled in our country, stated that '*when I am busy, my husband's second wife look after my children she hasn't got child she really helps me in every issue*'.

d1. When they go to a meeting (such as neighbors and relatives), they can give their opinions about the nursing home or care home

'What do you think about the nursing home where your children can get proper care when you go to a meeting (like neighbors and relatives meetings)?' The frequency distribution of the answers to the question is given in the following table.

Table 12: Opinions about nursing home or nursery where appropriate care for their child

Matter	f
We never hear the presence of such places	6
Care home or nursing home relaxes us	6
I do not want to leave my children in the care home or in the nursery	3

In this part of the work we asked mothers '*When you go to a meeting (such as neighbors and relatives meetings), what do you think about the nursing home or home where your children can get proper care?*' 6 mothers said they had never been informed of the existence of such places and had never investigated them. Then the mothers' nursing home or nursing home will comfort them at least. Mrs Saime, '*I haven't search for my child care home or home because I have not heard of such a place, but it would be good. At the least when I need to leave them for 1-2 hours and do my work*' she said. 6 mother '*care homes or nurseries relieve me*' use that expression.

Mrs Şükran '*Nursing homes? I do not know. I wish I would have left my children there at least when I needed. Sometimes I feel a little relaxed when they go to the school, there are already two children going to the school. Then I could devote some time to myself.*' "In this regard, the three mothers we interviewed indicated that they would not be able to leave

their children to the nursery or care home. About this subject Mrs Esma '*How do I leave my children to nursing home, do not they tell me what kind of a mother it is, do mothers leave their children to the nursing home? Never I leave my children there. As long as I am right, I will take care of them*' she said.

4. Discussion

Within the scope of the study, 10 mothers indicated more than one requirement about their material needs. In this context, 10 mothers stated that their expenses were heavy and they could not fulfill their children's wishes. 7 mothers said that couldn't pay the house rent. 7 mothers stated that they couldn't get the necessary tools and toys for their children. 6 mothers say that, just I can fill their bellies, 6 mothers say that I can't buy clothes for my children most of the time. Three mothers said that their children education expenses were too heavy so I can't pay for these. When the studies done in the literature are examined, it is seen that the material requirements of the parents of the children with intellectual disability (Evcimen 1996; Pearson and Sternberg 1986). Floyd and Saitzyk (1992) families with disabled children were found to have positive parental attitudes and supportive family structure, if their economic status were high. Farmer et al. (2004) reported that as the economic situation of the family declines and the costs of the family increase, the financial needs of the family increase more. Öztürk (2009), in his study, found that the requirements of mothers 'who have disabled child' are generally related to their economic situation. This finding of Öztürk it supports the findings of this research. In addition, the findings of Sucuoğlu (1995), which were obtained from researching that it was done in order to determine the needs of the parents with disabilities, also showed that most of the parents had material needs. This work of Sucuoğlu also supports the work done. In field studies, the opinions of families with a child who is generally inadequate were consulted and the findings of their financial needs were met. In this study, the opinions of the mothers who have children with three intellectual disabilities were consulted it has been seen that the mothers stated the most material need; it is understood from the fact that they have difficulty in feeding their children's abdomen. Therefore, it can be said that as the number of individuals with disabilities increases, the financial need increases.

Opinions about the information given by the mothers to environment about their intellectual disability children situation two items were tried to be examined. In the first issue, the views on how children describe their situation to their siblings are addressed, these opinions are like this. 4 of 11 mothers stated that they did not make any statements to their normal children because of the lack of information about the situation of children with intellectual disability. 4 mothers in the same scope stated that

normal children have more information about the situation of their intellectual disability siblings. Three of the mothers who participated in the study indicated that their normal children and children with intellectual disability children were grown together, so they did not feel the need to make any explanation. In this study, two mothers stated that their normal children didn't make any explanation because they were too young. Just a mother said that, she gave information about the feelings and behaviors of children with disabilities. Like other members of the family, special needs brothers and sisters also experience different feelings due to the disability of their siblings. They can usually experience emotions such as anger, frustration, and ignorance. The most important issue that the siblings fear is their concern that they will be disabled as well (Küçüker, 1997). In order to put an end to these worries and fears, the siblings of children with intellectual disability should be given necessary and clear information on the current situation of their disabled siblings. Because these children have difficulty understanding the features and cause of the obstacles in their siblings (Meyer, 1997; Meyer and Vadasy, 2006). For these reasons, it is very important to get enough information about the special needs children of the mothers and to transfer this information to the other children. In this work we did, seen that mothers in general couldn't tell the situation of their intellectual disability children to normal children. This may be due, in part, to the fact that mothers who have children with intellectual disability do not have enough information about their children situation, have difficulty in accessing information, and have to look at their children at home for most of their time.

The second item about the information that mother gives to environment about their intellectual disability children situation. The answer of mothers when neighbors, friends or foreigner ask their disabled children situation are as follows 7 mother's said that *'we says what they heard from teachers and doctors when someone ask about our children situation'*.

5 mothers, while explaining the situation of their children to their surroundings, stated that this situation came from God or that God's blessing. The mothers who were interviewed in the scope of the study we found that their children felt the need to explain to the public despite the fact that they did not have enough information about their children disabilities. Most of the intellectual disability individuals are immediately noticeable due to their physical characteristics, and their behaviors and reactions to certain situations can also differ from their peers. In these differences, they cause many difficulties to live, Emerson (2003). For these reasons, the family may be anxious about the possibility of a question that is always around, and they need more explanation from the surrounding area. Although attitudes towards children with disabilities are more positive nowadays, but the reason for the disability settled in society is seen as

mother and father, so parents need to explain more to the neighborhood, Küllü (2008). The work described above is parallel to the 'need for disclosure to the environment' of the work we have done.

Mothers' opinions on information requirements are addressed in 3 matters. The first of these matters related with how they teach their children some skills. In this regard, 5 mothers stated that they did not have enough time to teach some skills to their children. 4 mothers said they tried to teach some skills to their children, but they did not know exactly how to teach them. 4 mothers say that they repeat what they do to their children, while 3 mothers say that they do what teachers say.

Sarı, Baser and Turan (2006) the needs and care of the children takes a long time. Therefore, the mothers stated that they haven't enough time for them. It may be normal to have a lack of enough time to teach mothers children a skill when the number of children with special needs, the needs of other members of the family, and housework are considered. Sarı and their friends' expressions also support this matter. The second item about the information needs of the mothers is opinions about their children obstacles. 7 mothers stated that they haven't enough information about their children disabilities. 5 mothers in the same context stated that they have got information from the doctors about their children obstacle and 4 mothers stated that they have got information from the teachers about their children obstacle. In this context, when we evaluate the expressions of the mothers we interviewed, it has been determined that the mothers do not have detailed information about the disability, usually limited to what they hear from doctors or teachers. The fact that the mothers are limited to doctors and teachers as a source of information takes into account the difficulties of mothers in accessing information. These results are inevitable when the mothers are generally considered in terms of educational conditions and time problems. Expert teams to be created by the guidance research centers, a professional team to be formed in the hospital, services can be taken to families with at least several special needs children can be reached and information can be given. (Sucuoğlu, 1995) Families who have children with special needs stated that received information from doctors about their children disabilities and that the information and recommendations made were inadequate. In addition, there are very few services to inform and direct these families and that is why families constantly need information. This view of Sucuoğlu supports this finding of the work being done. The third item concerning the information needs of the mothers is about their opinions on the exchange of information with parents with other special needs children. In this context, 7 mothers said that it would be very helpful. 5 mothers stated that there was not enough time in this regard. 4 mothers said that they can learn new things from each other and they can support each other. In this regard, 2 mothers stated that they would not benefit.

In the study that Beck and Hastings (2004) did children with mental retardation performed positive family contributions, families with handicapped children like themselves families to come together and talk about their problems, affect them positively. Sucuoğlu (1995) found that mothers and fathers needed information intensively in their work to determine the needs of parents with disabilities. This work of Sucuoğlu supports this work.

It has been observed that Akçamete and Kargın's 'determination of the needs of mothers with hearing-impaired children' were also the 'information needs' of the dimension that mothers generally need. It supports the work done in this study.

The general support social service needs of the mothers who received the opinions within the scope of the research were examined in 4 items. In this context, the first matter of related to the need to talk more with the clergy whom they think they can help solve their problem. 6 mothers went to the clergy for the first intellectual disability children, but they did not see any benefit, and there was no difference in the case of their children. In this context, in this context, 4 mothers stated that when they talk to clergy, they were spiritually comfortable. 3 mothers used expressions that I never felt the need to go clergy.

It has been seen that people who are faced with an unwanted situation are held up by religion and are standing by their religious beliefs. (Rudolf H. Mass, 1988) In Evcimen's (1996) study on the Needs of Mentally Retarded Children's Mothers and Fathers, it was seen that parents needed to talk with clergyman about their support needs. Rudolf H. Mass's opinions and Evcimen's work findings support this article of study. The second item of work on this subject is concerned with mothers' opinions on a carer who supposed to take care of their children whenever necessary. 8 mother stated that it would be very good and the burden on them would be somewhat reduced. 6 mothers stated that they will spare a little time for themselves. 6 mothers stated that their economic situation makes it impossible, and 3 mothers stated that can not trust the caregiver. In almost all of the work done, mothers complain that they do not have the time for themselves or no time to do a house work. According to Zucman, (1982), mothers of intellectual disability children are consistently engaged in housework and child care, because of their broken life in social life, so that they do not have spare time to spare for them while they meet the care and needs of their children all day. Also, if there is no place for the mother to leave the child when the mother should go out, or if there is no babysitter, the mother has more problems. These statements support the work we have done.

As to what the mothers usually prefer to talk about their problems under the general support social service needs heading, 6 mothers stated that they wanted to talk to a psychologist or psychiatrist, 4 mothers wanted to talk to someone other than their

family, 2 mothers stated that they wanted to talk to their mother. Many studies with parents of children with mental retardation have reported that mothers and fathers are under more stress than mothers and fathers with normal children (Emerson, Robertson and Wood 2004; Dyson, 1997. Emerson (2003) found that 22% of mothers of children with mental impairment in the study of social and economic status, mental health status and social and psychological difficulties experienced by mothers with mental retardation and adolescents' mothers had a psychological condition related to their problems He stated. These works are parallel to the work done. When we look at the opinions of the mothers about the place where they will leave their children when they will attend a meeting (such as neighbors and relatives meetings), 7 of mothers stated that they could not leave their children at any time when they would attend a meeting (such as neighbors and relatives meetings). In this context, 4 mothers said that they left their children to relatives. 1 mother said that in such cases her husband's second wife looked after her children.

When you go to a meeting (such as neighbors and relatives meetings), what do you think about the nursing home or nursery home where your children can get proper care? 'for the question 6 mother stated that they had never been informed of the existence of such places and that they did not investigate at all and then they stated that the nursing home or nursery home would comfort them. 3 mothers stated that they would not leave their children to the nursery or to the nursing home.

In the work of Sucuoğlu (1995) to determine the needs of parents with disabilities, Akçamete and Kargın also pointed out that the '*determination of the needs of mothers with hearing impaired children*', it has been observed that the mothers expressed the need for General Support-Community Service. This supports the work. As a result, all of the mothers stated that they could not take time for themselves. Because of a large number of intellectual disability children in the family, housework, other children's care the mothers have indicated that they need time. Sarı et al. (2006) the needs of the children and the care they need take a very long time. Therefore, the mothers stated that they could not spend as much time for themselves. It may be normal to have not enough time to mother's teach some skills to their children when the number of intellectual disability children care and housework are considered. Sarı and of their friends expressions also support this substance. Almost all of mothers stated more than one requirement in the area of material requirements. The area that is most needed in the research is related to material requirements. In the scope of the research, the mothers whom we interviewed were found to have a second need. This is about information. In this context, mothers have indicated that they need more knowledge to teach their children some skills. All members of families with children with special needs want to get all the information about the intellectual disability family member

because they are faced with an unusual situation and this member of the family shows different characteristics and different behaviors from their peers. (Harris, 2008) This is confirmed by the fact that most of the work done by families with children with special needs require information. This supports the work done.

Sucuoğlu (1995), in the study of the needs of the parents of the handicapped children while parents indicated the most information need, their financial needs were in third place. Akçamete and Kargin (1996) investigate whether they have done so in order to determine the needs of mothers with hearing impairment. Mothers indicated the most information requirements. Secondly, they stated that their material requirements were higher. For this purpose; Mert (1997) studied the need of families which their children in different disability groups, the families needed the most information in this study. Öztürk (2011) also found that mothers preferred the most information needs in the study of determining the needs of families with disabilities and the family burden. While the need for information in the research findings of Sucuoğlu, Öztürk, Mert, Akçamete and Kargin was in the first place, in this study, mothers with at least 3 intellectual disability children expressed their most financial needs. This can be interpreted as the mother's more economic hardship. Source of distress may the abundance of children with disabilities, the type of disability and the economic situation of the family may have created this disparity. According to the data of this study, the general support-social service needs of the mothers are in the 3rd place. General support - On the community service side, some mothers have indicated that nursing homes and nurseries will meet the needs of mothers, while also indicating that they need a caregiver to take care of their children and that they are having trouble with where to leave their children when they go to an activity. General support - families benefiting from community services are understood from the results of most of the studies they feel strongly about. Families of children with disabilities whose responsibilities increase and whose roles and functions differ are in need of more support services. Mothers who are primarily responsible for the disabled individual are most likely to need support. Mothers give up the work life for the care of the handicapped child and delays his personal aims and desires. Therefore General support and community services should be done by professional staff should make both professional help and planning for social support in the family. (Çoban, 2002; Şimşek, 2002).

Regarding general support and community service, Akçamete and Kargin (1996) emphasize that they should regulate family relations and communication and also require specialist help to support them in some matters. These comments support the work being done. In relation to the need to explain the situation of their children; mothers also pointed out that they needed more help and information to tell the

situation of the children to their normal children, neighbors, friends or a foreigner. Families with low levels of education and socioeconomic status often have knowledge about what heard from environment about their intellectual disability children they are not adequately and correctly informed about their intellectual disability children. (Maloni, Despres, Habbous, Primmer, Slatten and Gibson, 2010).

Most of the mothers whose opinions are taken in this study either primary school graduates or illiterate. The level of education is the most important condition for achieving the current knowledge and for understanding and evaluating that knowledge correctly. Considering the education levels of the mothers covered by the interview, the information requirement may be considered normal.

When the needs of the mothers are examined according to the education levels, it can be said that the maternal needs have not changed at a significant level. In the study of Akçamete and Kargin (1996) it has been seen that needs of mothers with hearing-impaired children did not differ according to the educational level of their mother's needs. It doesn't matter if the level of education of the family is high or low, they may need information in case of special situation. This supports the work done. In conclusion, according to the findings of the research conducted, it was seen that, when the mothers with at least 3 children with intellectual disability were examined in terms of variables such as education status, number of children and financial status, it was first found that they had material needs and then they had information needs, social services utilization and disclosure requirements. In addition, when the related literature is examined, it is similar to the findings of the research of the parents with various special needs children.

5. Suggestions

Considering the problems encountered during the period of planning and finalizing the research and related literature reviews, the following suggestions can be made for the researches and applications to be made in the future.

5.1 Recommendations for Practice

1. Funds can be created for the financial needs of mothers who have multiple disabled children, and the maintenance fees they are currently receiving can be increased. They can be provided free of charge with services such as rent, fuel, electricity, water, transportation and communication they need most.
2. For information that mothers need, a unit can be created at the guidance and research center, and information can take to the mothers' home because of the mother's condition.

3. In order that the mothers can devote more time to themselves and they can take better care of their children, nurse to be provided by the state from the employment agency can be provided to the mothers.
4. Easy-to-access nursing homes or nursing homes can be built so that the mothers can participate in social activities or collective activities.

5.2 Suggestions for further research

1. The study can be done in different social circles with more subjects in order to make the research more generalizable.
2. Research can be done to include different family members.

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